

The HuT

Prototype of innovative insurance product

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3. The insurance role in DRR

Natural disasters (ND) can significantly affect infrastructure and properties, leading to substantial economic and human losses (Botzen et al., 2019; CRED & UNDRR, 2020). In the context of a rapidly changing climate and an increasing population, the impacts of ND are escalating exponentially (Berlemann & Steinhardt, 2017; Banholzer et al., 2014).

Insurance companies are increasingly becoming vital in supporting property owners, public sectors, and other impacted stakeholders (Botzen et al., 2019; Fisher & Surminski, 2012). The costs and consequences of ND cannot be managed solely by governments and necessitate the involvement of private companies. In this context, the role of insurance extends beyond traditional claims settlement. The escalating impact of ND demands a comprehensive approach to address these challenges. Consequently, insurance organizations are emerging as key partners in disaster risk reduction (DRR) measures (Kousky, 2019; Le Quesne et al., 2017). For instance, the latter study explores insurance mechanisms that can be integrated into broader DRR strategies to enhance resilience against natural disasters. Evidence and case studies demonstrate the effectiveness of insurance in mitigating financial losses and supporting recovery efforts post-disaster. Broadly speaking, the following key policy recommendations are proposed:

1. **Promote Public-Private Partnerships:** Encourage collaboration between governments and the private insurance sector to develop and implement effective insurance solutions for disaster risk management.
2. **Enhance Risk Assessment and Data Sharing:** Improve the collection, analysis, and sharing of risk data to better understand and manage disaster risks. This includes developing standardized methodologies for risk assessment.
3. **Increase Awareness and Education:** Raise awareness among stakeholders, including policymakers, businesses, and the public, about the benefits and mechanisms of insurance in disaster risk management.
4. **Develop Tailored Insurance Products:** Create insurance products that are specifically designed to address the unique risks and needs of different regions and communities, particularly those most vulnerable to natural disasters.
5. **Strengthen Regulatory Frameworks:** Establish and enforce regulatory frameworks that support the development and sustainability of insurance markets, ensuring that they are robust and capable of responding to disaster risks.
6. **Incorporate Insurance into National DRR Plans:** Integrate insurance solutions into national and local disaster risk reduction plans and strategies to ensure a comprehensive approach to managing disaster risks.
7. **Support Innovation in Insurance:** Encourage innovation in the insurance sector to develop new products and services that can better address emerging risks associated with climate change and natural disasters.

Developing these policies can be challenging and may encounter several issues, including those stemming from the insurance companies themselves. Additionally, the technical aspects of these policies are strongly correlated with the typical challenges faced by the insurance market. One of the primary issues is affordability and accessibility. Insurance premiums can be prohibitively expensive, particularly in high-risk areas prone to natural disasters. This often results in underinsurance or a lack of coverage among vulnerable populations. Ensuring that insurance products are accessible to all segments of the population, including low-income households, remains a significant challenge. Innovative solutions and subsidies are required to make insurance more affordable (Botzen et al., 2019; Fisher & Surminski, 2012). Another challenge is

the so-called adverse selection. This occurs when individuals with higher risks are more likely to purchase insurance, while those with lower risks opt out. This leads to a disproportionate number of high-risk policyholders, increasing the insurer's overall risk. To combat adverse selection, insurers need to implement better risk assessment tools and encourage broader participation through mandatory insurance schemes or incentives (Kousky, 2019; Le Quesne et al., 2017). Moral hazard is also a concern. This arises when the presence of insurance leads to riskier behavior by policyholders, who feel protected against losses. This can result in higher claims and increased costs for insurers. Insurers can mitigate moral hazard by incorporating deductibles, co-payments, and promoting risk-reducing behaviors through discounts and incentives. Mol et al. (2020) conducted a lab experiment with 357 participants to understand how different financial incentives, probability levels, and deductibles on self-insurance investments (in the ND market) influence investments in damage-reducing measures and the presence of moral hazard. Results proved that premium discounts and mitigation loans significantly increase investments in damage-reduction measures. These incentives help policyholders to better manage their risks and reduce potential losses from natural disasters. Additionally, moral hazard was observed in high-probability scenarios (15%) but not in low-probability scenarios (3%). This suggests that moral hazard is less of an issue in insurance markets where the probability of a loss is low. Policyholders are less likely to reduce their preventive measures when the likelihood of a disaster is low. Also, when policyholders face higher expected losses, they are more likely to invest in measures that reduce the potential damage. On a general view, policyholders that are more risk-averse, believe in the effectiveness of protective measures, and are more worried about flooding are more likely to invest in damage-reduction measures.

All these aspects should be reflected in the context of a changing climate and the resulting increase in the frequency of natural disasters. The frequency and severity of natural disasters are increasing due to climate change, leading to higher claims and financial losses for insurers (Banholzer et al., 2014; Born & Viscusi, 2006). This trend necessitates continuous adaptation of risk models and pricing strategies. Insurers are investing in advanced predictive analytics and climate modeling to better assess and price risks. Additionally, they are advocating for stronger building codes and disaster mitigation measures. Regulatory and compliance challenges add another layer of complexity. The regulatory landscape for insurance is constantly evolving, with new laws and regulations being introduced to protect consumers and ensure market stability. Compliance with these regulations can be costly and complex. Insurers need to invest in robust compliance management systems and stay informed about regulatory changes to avoid penalties and maintain trust with policyholders. The regulations are also facing a strong technological disruption that is transforming the insurance industry. Rapid advancements in technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and big data offer opportunities for innovation but also pose challenges in terms of integration and cybersecurity. Insurers must invest in upgrading legacy systems and training their workforce to leverage new technologies effectively. This requires significant financial and organizational commitment. These challenges require a multifaceted approach, combining technological innovation, regulatory compliance, and proactive risk management.

A recent systematic review (Kalfin et al., 2022) on these subjects explores the role of insurance also as a viable solution for sustainable economic recovery following natural disasters. The review identifies various types of disaster risk insurance, including agricultural, flood, property, earthquake, crop, and natural disaster insurance. Among these, agricultural, flood, and property insurance have been the most discussed in recent years, presumably because they are most influenced by climate change. Results prove that insurance is crucial for funding economic recovery after disasters. It helps mitigate the financial impact on affected communities and supports the rebuilding process. The availability of disaster risk insurance can expedite recovery and reduce the long-term economic impact of disasters. While there has been an annual increase

in the number of scientific publications on disaster risk insurance, reflecting growing interest and recognition of its importance, specific publications on the role of insurance companies in DRR are still sparse. The study emphasizes the need for ongoing research to improve the effectiveness of insurance in disaster risk management.

Few studies focus on practical examples of real events. Atreya et al. (2015) investigates the relationship between insurance and individual risk reduction activities, focusing on why these two might act as complements rather than substitutes. The study uses data from over 1,000 homeowners in New York City who experienced Hurricane Sandy in 2012. The paper finds that insurance and pre-disaster risk reduction measures, such as dry proofing buildings, tend to complement each other. Homeowners who purchase flood insurance are more likely to invest in long-term risk reduction measures. However, insurance acts as a substitute for emergency preparedness measures taken just before a disaster, like moving belongings to higher floors. The study identifies several behavioral mechanisms behind these relationships, including past flood damage experiences, federal disaster assistance, and psychological factors influencing risk perception. Financial incentives or regulations might be necessary to encourage insured individuals to adopt emergency preparedness measures. The paper concludes that understanding the complementary and substitute relationships between insurance and risk reduction activities can help design better policies to enhance disaster resilience. Another study by Surminski & Hudson (2017) explores how disaster insurance can contribute to risk reduction, focusing on Europe. It highlights that while insurance is theoretically recognized for its potential to reduce risks, practical linkages between insurance and risk reduction efforts are often lacking. Various methodologies are analyzed to assess and enhance these linkages, using several European case studies as examples. These case studies include flood insurance in England, wildfire insurance in Portugal, and flood and drought risk in the Po River basin in Italy. Results emphasize the importance of multisectoral partnerships (MSPs) in strengthening the risk reduction potential of insurance schemes. The concept of MSPs involves collaboration between various stakeholders, including the private sector, government entities, and civil society organizations. These partnerships aim to address the complex challenges of disaster risk management by leveraging the strengths and resources of each sector. MSPs facilitate better coordination and collaboration among different stakeholders, ensuring that disaster risk reduction efforts are comprehensive and well-integrated. This includes sharing information, resources, and expertise to develop more effective insurance schemes. By bringing together diverse perspectives and capabilities, MSPs can foster innovative approaches to disaster risk management. This can lead to the development of new insurance products and risk reduction strategies that are more tailored to the specific needs and contexts of different regions. Additionally, MSPs can play the role of policy and regulatory supporter, helping the alignment of insurance schemes with broader policy and regulatory frameworks, ensuring that they support national and international disaster risk reduction goals. This aspect is manifest also in local communities, where the adoption of MPSs allows a better understanding and management of disaster risks, also with the inclusion of training, education, and best practice development.

4. Innovation in insurance

As mentioned above, the frequency and intensity of natural disasters have increased in recent years due to phenomena such as climate change and population growth in risk-prone areas. These disasters, including floods, droughts, landslides, heatwaves, hurricanes, and extreme temperatures, have a significant impact on macroeconomic outcomes and the financial stability of countries. While catastrophe insurance can mitigate the effects of such events, only a portion of climate-related losses is currently insured. This discrepancy between risk exposure and insurance coverage is defined as the "protection gap." The protection gap represents a significant challenge for economic and social resilience, as it leaves individuals, businesses, and governments vulnerable to the financial consequences of natural disasters. In Europe, only a quarter of climate-related losses are insured, with some countries having coverage below 5% (1, web reference). This situation is particularly concerning in Italy, where about 97% of losses due to earthquakes and floods between 1980 and 2022 were uninsured (2, web reference). The protection gap is attributable to both demand and supply factors. Low risk awareness, the complexity of insurance policies, high prices, and the expectation of post-disaster public aid can discourage the demand for insurance. On the supply side, insurance companies may be reluctant to cover rare but high-impact catastrophic events due to the difficulty of modeling such risks and the uncertainty associated with climate change.

Among possible strategies to reduce the natural risk coverage gap, it should be recognized that it is crucial to raise risk awareness among the public and improve transparency in the insurance sector. Well risk informed citizens and businesses will be more likely to seek protection and adopt mitigation measures that reduce the risk of losses and improve insurance supply conditions. Insurance companies, in turn, must strive to simplify contract language and improve transparency in pricing and coverage conditions. Furthermore, a multifaceted approach involving governments, regulators, and the insurance sector is essential.

Innovative insurance solutions can play a crucial role in reducing the gap and improving resilience. Innovation presents itself as a crucial tool to address this challenge, both from the supply and demand sides of insurance.

On the supply side, innovation allows insurance companies to:

- Develop more accurate climate risk prediction models that take into account the effects of climate change. Traditionally, models were based on historical data, but innovation enables the simulation of climate evolution using advanced global circulation models, allowing for better assessment of future risks and the creation of more targeted insurance products.
- Offer a wider range of products and services, not limited to merely reacting to catastrophic events, but also including prevention, anticipation, resilience, and support for businesses and private citizens to face the challenges of climate change.
- Adopt insurtech/climatech solutions, which offer new capabilities for risk assessment and claims management.

On the demand side, innovation can help to:

- Increase risk awareness among citizens and businesses, encouraging them to seek greater protection and adopt risk mitigation measures.
- Improve the clarity and transparency of insurance contracts, making it easier for potential customers to understand the terms and conditions of coverage and pricing.
- Facilitate access to insurance through digital and mobile platforms, simplifying the process of purchasing and managing policies.

Innovation, therefore, acts on multiple fronts to reduce the protection gap, making insurance more accessible, affordable, and suited to the needs of a constantly evolving world. Some of the most discussed innovations, for the insurance sector, include the following:

- The use of satellite imagery and connected sensors to collect real-time data and assess risks more accurately.
- The development of digital platforms that simplify the process of purchasing and managing policies.
- Climate risk forecasting models: Insurance companies are focusing on climate risk projecting models that incorporate the effects of climate change, allowing for more accurate risk assessment and better pricing.
- Parametric insurance: this type of insurance provides automatic payouts based on the occurrence of a predefined event, such as an earthquake of a certain magnitude or a flood exceeding a certain threshold. Parametric insurance can speed up claims payments and reduce administrative costs, making it particularly suitable for natural disasters.
- Microinsurance: Designed to provide affordable insurance coverage to low-income populations, microinsurance can use mobile technology to reach new customers and simplify underwriting and claims processes.
- Public-private partnerships: Collaboration between governments and insurance companies can help develop sustainable and accessible insurance programs, with governments providing financial support or incentives to increase participation.

In conclusion, the protection gap for natural risks represents an urgent challenge that requires coordinated action from all stakeholders. Innovative insurance solutions, along with effective public policies and increased risk awareness, can help bridge the gap, protecting individuals, businesses, and the global economy from the devastating consequences of natural disasters.

Within The HuT, and specifically in the activities described in this report, some of these innovations have been evaluated and developed through the design and implementation of prototype insurance products. Specifically, parametric insurance and Community Based Catastrophe Insurance (CBCI) have been selected for such a development. Thanks to interactions with Demonstrators 3 (Lattari Mountains) and 8 (Ogliastra Region), it has been possible to collect granular and specific data essential for this development process. These demonstrators have also provided valuable feedback on the efficacy and practicality of the developed products.

4.1. The parametric insurance

Parametric insurance policies represent an innovative insurance solution that differs from traditional policies by defining an objective and measurable parameter related to the risky event, the exceeding of which triggers automatic compensation. Unlike traditional policies, which require a detailed assessment of the damages incurred, parametric policies are based on a predetermined and objective approach, simplifying the claims process and making it more transparent and faster.

Parametric insurance policies, also known as index-based policies, are insurance contracts where the payment of compensation is linked to the occurrence of a specific and predetermined event, defined as a trigger event, whose intensity must exceed a predefined threshold, measured by an objective parameter or index. In other words, the payment is not tied to the quantification of the actual damage suffered but to the exceeding of an intensity threshold of the trigger event. For example, a parametric earthquake policy might provide for the payment of a predetermined sum if the earthquake's magnitude exceeds a certain value, regardless of the actual damage suffered by the insured.

The choice of parameter or index is crucial for the policy's effectiveness. The parameter must be:

- Objective and measurable: it must be possible to unambiguously determine if the threshold has been exceeded.
- Related to the risk: there must be a statistically significant relationship between the parameter and the potential damage.
- Available from independent sources: the data related to the parameter must be provided by reliable third parties.

Parametric policies offer several advantages over traditional policies, including:

- Speed of settlement: compensation is paid out very quickly, often within a few days of the trigger event, without the need for complex assessments. This is particularly important in emergency situations where timely assistance is crucial.
- Transparency and certainty: the conditions for activating the policy are clear and predefined, eliminating ambiguities and potential disputes over the extent of the damage. Both the insured and the insurer know the terms of the contract in advance, fostering mutual trust.
- Coverage of non-traditional risks: parametric policies allow for the insurance of risks that are difficult to quantify with traditional policies, such as business interruptions or lost profits. This is possible thanks to the flexibility in choosing the parameter, which can be adapted to the specific needs of the insured.
- Cost reduction: the automation of the settlement process and the elimination of assessments reduce administrative costs, making premiums more competitive.
- Accessibility in emerging markets: parametric policies are particularly suitable for countries with limited insurance infrastructure, offering effective solutions for risk management in vulnerable contexts.

Parametric policies are applied in various sectors, such as agriculture, where they are used to protect farmers from crop losses caused by extreme weather events such as droughts, frosts, or storms. For agricultural purposes, the parameters used can include precipitation levels, temperature, or vegetation index. Another important use case is given by coverages related to catastrophic risks, that is, to protect against events such as earthquakes, hurricanes, or floods. In this case, policies could be activated when the event's intensity exceeds the predefined threshold, facilitating a rapid emergency response. Other use cases include transport and logistics, e.g., to cover delivery delays due to natural events. Here, parameters can be related to weather conditions or traffic levels; tourism and events to protect operators from cancellations due to bad weather (heavy rain, wind, or extreme temperatures).

Over the years, several parametric insurance programs have been implemented, including:

- Caribbean Catastrophe Risk Insurance Facility (CCRIF): offers parametric policies to Caribbean and Central American countries for protection against hurricanes, earthquakes, excessive rainfall, and drought.
- African Risk Capacity (ARC): provides parametric policies to African countries for managing risks related to drought, floods, and tropical cyclones.
- Pacific Catastrophe Risk Assessment and Financing Initiative (PCRAFI): supports Pacific countries in managing risks related to hurricanes, earthquakes, and tsunamis.

Despite the numerous advantages, parametric policies also present some challenges and limitations. Among these there is the possibility that the risk represented by the parameter does not accurately reflect the actual damage suffered. This can occur if the damaging event is caused by factors other than those considered by the parameter or if the data used for its definition is inaccurate or incomplete. Another issue is given by difficulties in identifying suitable datasets. Indeed, creating effective parametric policies requires reliable and high-quality data, which is not always available, especially in developing countries. Finally, since parametric policies are less

flexible than traditional ones, as compensation is tied exclusively to exceeding the predefined parameter, parametric policies can suffer from a certain lack of flexibility. This can lead to situations where the insured does not receive any compensation despite suffering damage, or vice versa.

To mitigate these challenges, some actions to pursue in the design of a parametric product have been identified. These include the focus on data quality, in particular new technologies could provide valuable sources such as satellite images and IoT sensors. Moreover, customizing parameters, in order to meet the specific needs of the insured and considering the risk characteristics and geographical context, could further help to build more effective products. This approach could include the adoption of multi-level triggers that combine different parameters to reduce the impact of any discrepancies between the parameter and the actual damage. Finally, developing dynamic parametric policies, e.g., using real-time data to update parameters and payments, it is possible to improve the congruence between actual conditions at the time of the event and indexes.

4.2. Community Based Catastrophe Insurance (CBCI)

Numerous reports and observatories have highlighted a significant gap in natural hazard protection, affecting human safety, properties, and economic activities. This insurance gap may be attributed to various factors, including challenges in securing resources, underestimation of risk potentials, and a lack of trust in insurance.

Community Based Catastrophe Insurance (CBCI) constitutes an insurance solution that promises to help communities to fill the finance risk gap by means of a collective underwriting provided by a public or collective representative entity. Among different reasons for looking to CBCI as a way to facilitate the provisioning of insurance companies, it should be observed that, when events are registered, damaged and affected people act as communities. Thus, looking at community strategies for a risk management approach that considers insurance as a key tool should be explored as a natural way to deal with the protection gap. Based on first experiences, CBCI enhances financial resilience for communities and residents. Insured residents and businesses tend to recover more effectively and swiftly after disasters. CBCI helps reduce the community's potential financial liabilities from catastrophes, improves its credit risk profile, speeds up the recovery process for those insured, and supports the economic revitalization of the community post-disaster. Additionally, CBCI can, potentially, make insurance more accessible by reducing premium costs, ensuring coverage after losses, and providing premium discounts for mitigation efforts at both community and household levels.

Eventually, CBCI could be designed in order to create incentives for risk reduction at both community and individual levels, facilitating premium discounts for mitigation efforts at the community and household levels and supporting funding for risk reduction activities through a premium surcharge. Communities adopting this solution could improve the decision-making capability on risk reduction through risk analysis and pricing. Unlike standard catastrophe insurance, which applies to individual properties, CBCI provides a mechanism for financial incentives for community-scale mitigation. It can also encourage individuals to engage in location-specific risk reduction efforts and potentially enhance or build social capital within the community.

Bernhardt et al. (2021), evidences the following four possible implementations of CBCI strategy:

- **Facilitator Model:** In this approach, the community collaborates with an insurer to secure favorable insurance terms for residents and promotes awareness to boost the demand for

catastrophe insurance. The community does not handle premium payments or claims distribution.

- Group Policy Model: Here, the community arranges catastrophe insurance on behalf of its members, negotiates policy terms with the insurer, collects fees or charges, and pays the premium. The insurance contract remains between the property owner and the insurer, with claims paid directly to the property owner.
- Aggregator Model: In this model, the community directly purchases a policy from an insurer or reinsurer to cover multiple properties within its area. The community acts as the insured party and allocates funds based on the agreed terms in the contract.
- Community Captive Model: This model involves a local entity establishing its own captive insurance company, fully owned and controlled by the local entity. The captive functions like a standard insurance company: it collects premiums, issues policies, pays claims, accesses reinsurance or excess insurance, and can issue insurance-linked securities if needed.

The community's involvement and responsibility increase progressively from the first to the fourth model. Sources indicate that in all scenarios, the community might offer coverage for property owners to purchase voluntarily, or there could be instances where the community mandates residents to buy coverage.

5. Nat cat models

Nat cat models have been largely adopted by insurance companies to assess the financial risk arising from catastrophic events caused by natural hazards such as hurricanes, earthquakes, floods, and landslides. The models use data on past events to estimate the probability and severity of future events, considering the insurer's exposure, often in terms of properties in risk areas. The final output is the exceedance probability (EP) curve, which shows the probability that a certain financial loss will be exceeded.

Insurance companies use catastrophic models for various purposes, including:

- Determining the price of risk as it helps setting appropriate premiums based on the actual risk.
- Justifying solvency capital requirements since the models allow the computation of the capital needed to cover potential losses. Solvency II, the European framework for insurance regulation, requires the use of a standard formula or an internal model for catastrophic risk assessment.
- Assisting in risk diversification in terms of exposure to different types of catastrophes and diversification of the portfolio to reduce overall risk.
- Assessing the need for reinsurance, allowing the determination of how much risk to transfer to a reinsurer (if needed).
- Setting policy conditions, defying deductibles and other contractual clauses.
- Portfolio optimization, allowing the evaluation of the distribution of potential losses and optimization of the portfolio to maximize returns and minimize risk.
- Controlling the price of catastrophe bonds, assessing the risk of these financial instruments and setting their price.
- Organizing emergency plans, predicting the impact of a catastrophe and preparing response plans to manage claims and provide assistance to clients.

It is important to note that catastrophic models are simplifications of complex natural processes and heavily depend on input data. Their accuracy and reliability are crucial for the robustness of the insurance sector. However, building accurate models is complex, requiring the use of comprehensive historical data and high spatial resolution data, as well as expertise in multiple scientific disciplines such as earth sciences and civil engineering. The lack of comprehensive historical data, especially for low-frequency, high-severity events, represents one of the most significant challenges in this context. Usually, different software and service companies develop and provide nat cat models for the insurance industry for specific risks, often at a country level, based on their best effort on retrieving historical data and building physical models for both hazard and vulnerability. However, simpler models, e.g. based on hazard maps and empirical vulnerability relationships, can be profitably used as tools for exploring insurance products.

In order to support the design of the insurance products proposed in The HuT project, specific catastrophic models based on data collected from Demonstrator 3 and Demonstrator 8, respectively for the Landslide product and Wildfire product, have been developed. The use of ad-hoc catastrophic models offers the following advantages:

- The possibility to base the insurance cost on known risk elements through the state-of-the-art knowledge of hazard and vulnerability from a scientific perspective.
- The ability to operate in the absence of actuarial datasets, i.e., a statistically significant experience of exposures and claims.
- The ability to explore the effects of risk concentration and, in general, the evaluation of different geographical configurations of portfolio distribution.

While insurance companies usually adopt proprietary models that take advantage of the knowledge shared along many companies and countries, the possibility to run specifically developed models enable the possibility to calibrate them on data collected by Demonstrators, to specify custom view on risk that help the exploration of innovative pricing approaches, as a constant payout and the bulk customer acquisition, associated, respectively with the parametric and CBCI insurance. Nevertheless, some simplifications have been assumed to compensate for the missing information, in particular with reference to vulnerability models.

Broadly speaking, catastrophe models are composed of hazard, vulnerability and finance modules. In Figure 1 a representation of the structure and main steps of the implemented models is represented. The hazard module is exploited building a Stochastic Event Set (SES) representative of the frequency and severity of the events, comprising variables that constitute vulnerability parameters. The intersection between the SES and a portfolio, and the correspondent damage estimate, leads to the identification of “virtual” claims associated with each simulated event. Aggregating such claims by policies produces the characterization of the risk. Similarly, the claim aggregation by event produces the Event Loss Table (ELT) constituted by the total loss of each event. Such event losses provide important information for assessing the portfolio risk.

Figure 1: Scheme of the developed nat cat models.

5.1. Simplified modeling approach proposed

5.1.1. Hazard module

The hazard module can simulate events dynamics through a procedure that proceeds in annual steps, summarized as follows:

1. The number of events in a simulation year is estimated.
2. Each event is assigned to a specific location based on the hazard map, which describes the average probability of an event occurring at each point in the territory.
3. Size and shape consistent with the available historical data are assigned to each event.
4. The procedure is repeated for the required number of years.

This technique is iterated for a certain number of years to create a synthetic set of events, representative of the characteristics and variability of the analyzed peril. This set of events is called the SES and is subsequently used for analyzing the effects of the phenomenon on a given portfolio.

5.1.2. Vulnerability Module

The vulnerability module of a catastrophe model for natural hazards is a crucial component that quantifies the degree of damage that at-risk structures may sustain due to a given event. The representation of vulnerability is often represented in the form of vulnerability curves, which show the probability of different levels of damage as a function of the event's intensity. The selection of some susceptibility factors could help reduce the uncertainty associated with the relationship between hazard characterization and damage. For example, in the case of an earthquake, factors such as magnitude, distance from the epicenter, and the construction characteristics of buildings are considered.

In the models developed for the prototype products presented here, the vulnerability module has been built based either on the information provided by Demonstrators or other information collected from the literature. More details are reported on the specific product sections.

5.1.3. Finance Module

The finance module consists of functionalities for representing sets of policies, i.e., insurance portfolios.

This module provides the following tools:

- A tool for importing existing portfolios
- A tool for creating synthetic portfolios
- Analysis of claims evaluation related to each SES event, a set of events, or all SES events
- Aggregation of claims for pricing purposes
- Aggregation of claims per event for risk assessment

In the development of the products illustrated in the next sections, the finance module has been used to produce the elements of the pricing strategy. Further details about the derivation of such elements are described in the following subsections.

5.2. Reference portfolio definition

The assessment of the cost of insurance coverage must consider, in addition to the characterization of the risk in the geographical location where each exposure is located, the risk related to the impact of an event on the entire portfolio elements that the insurance company will insure. Financial mutuality within a given portfolio is indeed an essential element of the sustainability of the insurance product. This financial sustainability can also be complemented by other risk financing tools, some of which may include:

- risk diversification within the company's activities
- reinsurance coverage
- financial instruments for transferring risk to investors, such as Catastrophe (Cat) bonds
- other financial tools and strategies

To accomplish such evaluations, it is necessary to refer to a representative portfolio configuration. For the development of the products synthetic portfolios have been built based on urban density and the number of businesses representative of a possible real portfolio.

5.3. Pricing modeling

The determination of the total premium, or finite premium (FP), is obtained as the sum of the pure premium (PP) and the cost of capital (CC):

$$FP = PP + CC$$

The respective definitions and estimation methodologies adopted in this activity are:

- Pure premium (PP): given by the specific cost of each exposure unit obtained as the average, evaluated over a sufficiently long period, of the cost of claims associated with that single exposure. This is determined, for each point of the territory, through catastrophic modeling, determining a virtual portfolio distributed on a fixed grid characterized by constant exposure.
- Cost of capital (CC): the cost of the capital necessary to cover the total claims related to the most significant events (defined based on a certain probability level) for which solvency must be guaranteed through dedicated capital. This cost is allocated for each exposure unit. The estimation of this component is described by the following expression:

$$CC = PP \cdot \lambda \cdot \frac{VaR^{200}}{AAL}$$

where (AAL) is the Average Annual Loss, estimated by the catastrophic model with reference to the reference portfolio; λ coefficient accounts for risk diversification, return of investments, and other cost of capital factors, herein qualitatively estimated and posed equal to 0.05; (VaR^{200}) is the so-called value at risk related to events with a return period of 200 years. The latter value is estimated as the difference between the cost of the expected loss with a return period of 200 years and the AAL:

$$VaR^{200} = Loss^{200} - AAL$$

The $Loss^{200}$ is obtained from the analysis of the catastrophic model results, specifically by aggregating the claims obtained from the intersection of the SES with the reference portfolio per year and constructing the AEP (Aggregate Exceedance Probability) curve from which the value corresponding to the probability value related to the 200-year return period is extracted.

$$FP = PP \cdot m$$

$$m = \lambda \frac{VaR^{200}}{AAL} + 1$$

Finally, the above analysis is related to the premium rates by normalizing with respect to the exposure:

$$PPR_i = \frac{PP_i}{Exposure_i}$$

$$FPR = PPR \cdot m$$

Where PPR and FPR are, respectively, the pure premium and the finite premium rates, obtained normalizing by the exposure amount.

For the derivation of insurance product pricing artifacts, a pure premium rate map and an AEP curve are derived crossing the SES events with, respectively, a virtual gridded portfolio with unit exposure and the reference portfolio. Finally, the finite premium rate map is obtained by multiplying the pure premium rate map to the m coefficient estimated as described above.

6. Landslide prototype product: DEM 3

6.1. Product concept

An insurance innovative product has been proposed in Demonstrator 3 to manage the risk related to rain-induced landslides. In the framework of the upcoming historical change in the Italian regulatory system for nat cat insurance for businesses, the product represents a useful tool also for future application of this kind of products in different contexts. Indeed, in the first months of 2025, all the businesses located in the Italian territory will be obliged to enroll in an insurance plan for natural events. The obligation is related to the following natural hazards: earthquakes, floods, and landslides. More details about this new legislation will be given in the upcoming months, but it is manifest how the context of the subjects treated in this deliverable will have an impact on the products that will be delivered in the next few years.

The product “Landslide First Rescue” is an innovative insurance product designed to help businesses and citizens manage the initial emergency caused by landslides triggered by heavy rainfall. The policy is underwritten based on the exposure of assets at risk of landslides. Claims are automatically generated when predefined rainfall thresholds are exceeded, and the user confirms the damage with media devices or other evidence. The claim is then quickly settled with a fixed compensation to assist with emergency management. Thus, the claims are not dependent on the actual characteristics of the events, i.e. the landslide’s movement type or extension. This approach removes the need of insurance adjusters and accelerates the settlement process that, especially in the case of largely impacted events, can take several weeks or months. In this view, “Landslide First Rescue” could be considered a complement to other insurance solutions that cover damage to assets caused by landslides.

The structure of the product is outlined hereafter following the guidelines suggested by the Insurance Distribution Directive (IDD). In particular, in the following sub-paragraphs, the main parts of the IDD product information template are exploited to describe the product. An implementation of the Insurance Information Product is also reported, with the sole purpose of showing a possible realization of the product.

6.1.1. What is insured?

The product provides a fixed compensation to manage the emergencies related to landslides events impacting some assets. This amount is predefined in the insurance agreements and is based on nat cat modeling. More details on the distribution of premium rates will be given in the next sections. An overview of the product information document is shown in Figure 2.

6.1.2. What is not insured?

The product does not cover the direct damage to tangible assets, i.e., buildings, lands, and their contents, comprising plant and machinery, industrial and commercial installations, related to landslides events. The product does not provide any fixed compensation from perils other than landslides. Additionally, it does not cover losses related to personal or company liability, and business interruption.

Landslide First Rescue Insurance

Insurance Product Information Document

Disclaimer: this document does not refer to a real insurance product. It is intended just to represent key information of a prototype product.

What is this type of insurance?

Landslide First Rescue is an insurance product that offers a fixed payout to manage the immediate emergencies related to impacted landslide events. The claim activation is related to specific rainfall thresholds and media device proofs or similar evidence. The settlement does not require the involvement of adjusters.

What is insured?

✓ Businesses of any kind subject to the effect of rainfall induced landslides.

What is not insured?

✗ Direct or indirect damage related to landslides or any kind of related hazards also different from landslides.

Are there any restrictions on cover?

! Limits in coverage are not defined.

Where am I covered?

✓ Monti Lattari region (Campania, Italy)

What are my obligations?

- The policyholder must provide information about the status of the buildings and promises where the policy is referred to.
- In case of rainfall threshold exceeding, to activate the claims-related processes, the policy holder must provide a media device proof or other form of evidence
- Other typical insurance obligations

When and how do I pay?

No specific payment details are needed

When does the cover start and end?

The coverage start day is the one manifest in the policy. It is automatically renewed at the end of every year if no rescission is provided.

How do I cancel the contract?

The policy can be cancelled following usual methods adopted for similar products

Figure 2: Landslide First Rescue product information document.

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6.1.3. Where is the product valid?

The product is applicable in the Monti Lattari region, where the pricing has been specifically implemented. The financial sustainability of the product within this geographic area has not been examined. However, this approach could potentially be extended to other regions, offering similar benefits in terms of pricing.

6.2. Interactions with Demonstrator 3

During the prototype development, an in-person meeting was organized at the Sorrento municipality in collaboration with CMCC and UNISA. A diverse group of stakeholders participated in the discussion, including the Mayor of Sorrento, the Chief of the Councilors, the Head of the Beach Club Businesses, several municipal technicians, and partners from CMCC. The meeting yielded numerous outcomes, particularly concerning the general perspectives of local business owners on the insurance market. In this context, the challenges that potential stakeholders might encounter are primarily related to jurisdictional matters. For instance, there are questions regarding the responsibility for damages caused by landslides on municipal territories adjacent to local businesses (e.g., municipal cliffs affecting private beach clubs). All involved stakeholders concurred on the implementation of mitigation measures, provided that some form of tax refund or insurance policy discount would be applied. The formal obligation to adopt natural catastrophe insurance in the coming months presents significant challenges for Italian businesses. Unresolved issues regarding the characteristics and liability of settlements remain under discussion. Policyholders may lose confidence in insurance if settlements are denied following an impacted event. Consequently, the discussion about the presented prototype has not been entirely satisfactory, despite some general appreciation for the fixed recovery and quick payout features.

6.3. Data and Methods

The above-mentioned nat cat model structure has been adopted to simulate the occurrence and related potential economic losses of landslides in the Monti Lattari region (Campania, Italy). The adoption of catastrophe models to depict impacts on local districts can be quite challenging. Indeed, the strength of this kind of modeling approach is the simulations of numerous events, both spatially and temporally. While the temporal aspect can be standardly reproduced, simulating a large number of years (and thus a large number of landslide areas) arbitrarily in this limited spatial extension is challenging. This aspect could produce an overestimation of the landslide frequency if it is not adequately calibrated. A solution to this issue has been proposed, weighing the magnitude of the event (proportional to the landslide area) on the whole Italian territory. This is not true for the landslide hazard that is based merely on the Monti Lattari region. In this way, we have been able to reproduce the phenomenon in a more comprehensive way, considering a wider range of magnitudes. It is worth noting that the hazard module in this case is represented by a susceptibility map developed from the results by Loche et al. (2022). These kinds of maps consider numerous variables, historical records, geomorphological variables, and specific statistical techniques to avoid the uneven spatial distribution of landslide data. The maps are developed from multiple landslide types: complex, deep seated gravitational slope deformation, diffused fall, fall, rapid flow, shallow, slow flow, and translational. In this application, we have considered the maximum values among the whole landslide kinds for every point in the map. A target resolution of 500m has been adopted, following the maximum resolution adopted

for each datasets used to develop the landslide susceptibility maps. The methodology presented by Loche et al. (2022) is unique in the literature as it incorporates crucial elements such as data heterogeneity, bias mitigation, and uncertainty estimation. The map we developed for the evaluation of the distribution of landslides phenomena in the Italian territory, zoomed on the DEM 3 area of interest, is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Susceptibility areas for the Monti Lattari and surrounding areas. Reddish color depict higher values, and thus zones prone to landslides.

While the above-mentioned susceptibility map depicts the areas more prone to landslides, both historically and physically, the other fundamental information needed for the characterization of the cat model is the historical rate of events per year. This information can be quite tricky to retrieve on large areas since the historical datasets are not homogeneous and may lead to misleading considerations. For the DEM3 area, however, CMCC provided a comprehensive list of past events that allowed us to retrieve this information. They adopt as reference several catalogues currently available over Italy: Franeltalia (Calvello & Pecoraro, 2018), Peruccacci et al. (2023), Franceschini et al. (2022). After some data filtering, the value of 30 events/year has been adopted. These datasets allowed the complete definition of the hazard module, as described in the section above.

The vulnerability module is defined using general simplifications due to the limited information available on classifying landslide-related damage to infrastructures. Unlike earthquakes and floods, for which specific vulnerability curves are well-documented and widely used (see Rossetto

et al., 2014 for a review), there is no general consensus for landslides. The diverse nature of landslide movements and characteristics makes it difficult to categorize damage phenomena uniformly. Due to the lack of data on past events and damage to specific infrastructures, we implemented an analytical function to map damage based on specific landslide characteristics. We chose the landslide area as the key factor influencing landslide magnitude. Although this is a broad simplification considering the various types of landslides, it enables a coherent classification of phenomena from a catastrophe modeling perspective.

The reference portfolio has been synthetically generated distributing policies proportionally to the urban density (Figure 4). For this purpose, the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) dataset (specifically the GHS-BUILT-S subset), produced within the Copernicus Emergency Management Service, has been adopted as a probability map where to place policies. The Istat Active Business Statistical Register (ASIA) estimates a number of businesses in the Campania region, equal to 379,190 (out of a total of 4,665,423 in Italy). Here, for the Monti Lattari area, and considering the uncertainty about possible market penetration of the product, a number of policies equal to 1000 has been considered to generate the synthetic portfolio. An exposure amount has been randomly associated to each policy with a value in the range 10,000-300,000 €, selected as a possible range of variation of building/content exposed values.

Figure 4: Locations of the exposures within the developed synthetic portfolio in the Monti Lattari region. The portfolio is concentrated in more densely populated areas.

6.4. Pricing

The annual premium is reckoned following the approach described in Section 4.3, that is, deriving a FPR map based on the PPR map and a coefficient that reflects the cost of capital to be added to the pure premium. The PPR map (see Figure 5) is created using specific catastrophe modeling techniques above-mentioned, with reference to a unitary gridded portfolio. The calculation of FPR incorporates the Value at Risk (VaR) estimate over a 200-year return period for the reference

portfolio. This value reflects the financial, underwriting, and solvency risks. This approach ensures that the premium accurately reflects the risk exposure and potential financial impact of catastrophic events.

Figure 5: Pure premium rate for the Monti Lattari region.

We have also been able to simulate the Aggregate Exceedance Probability (AEP) and Occurrence Exceedance Probability (OEP) curves, depicting the relationship among loss and return periods. The two curves represent two distinct aspects of the loss, since OEP focuses on individual events, while AEP considers the aggregate impact of all events within the period. In general terms, OEP is often used for pricing and underwriting single-event policies, whereas AEP is more relevant for portfolio management and reinsurance. The curves are shown in Figure 6. The difference between the curves suggests that multiple events are likely within the given time period. The AEP curve, which accounts for the cumulative impact of all events, is higher than the OEP curve, which only considers the largest single event. This implies that while individual events may not be extremely severe, the total impact of multiple smaller events can be substantial. With the hypothesized exposures, the mean cost of a single claim in each year is in the order of 7000 €, while the total loss by year is in the range of 50,000 €.

Figure 6: AEP and OEP curves for the synthetic portfolio shown above.

For the sake of completeness, a representative rainfall threshold panel for the city of Sorrento is shown in Table 1. The degrees represent the severity of the watch/warning/alarm status, while the last row includes the respective values of rainfall in mm. These thresholds are commonly used by Civil Protection to manage the hydrogeological risk in the Campania region. Here, we hypothesize that the claim activation (and thus the fixed compensation) could be related to these values.

Table 1: Rainfall threshold panel for the Sorrento town.

	Watch					Warning					Alarm					
Duration (h)	3	6	24	48	72	3	6	24	48	72	1	3	6	24	48	72
Threshold (mm)	43	51	66	79	94	57	66	86	104	123	49	66	78	101	121	145

Finally, the distribution of premiums, considering the reference portfolio, for the “Landslide First Rescue” has been estimated associating each policy to the finite premium rate of the relative geographical position (see Figure 7). The average yearly premium value is equal to 30 €.

Figure 7: Distribution of premiums of the Landslide First Rescue reference portfolio.

7. Wildfire prototype product: DEM 8

7.1. Product concept

Based on the Italian regulatory framework, its implications regarding the role of insurance in the catastrophic risk reduction system, and the possibilities of integrating the currently available insurance offer through innovative products, it was decided to propose, within the project, an insurance product that offers companies coverage for direct damage to buildings and their contents as a result of wildfires. This insurance product is called “Fire Safe Community” and is designed to meet the following needs:

- to provide companies with additional insurance coverage for natural risks, including the new mandatory insurance for Italian companies, specifically for direct damage caused by wildfires. While the new insurance requirement covers direct damage from floods, earthquakes, and landslides, it does not explicitly include coverage for other natural hazards, such as wildfires.
- to establish a reward mechanism for risk reduction actions through the reduction of the insurance coverage cost.

Similarly to the landslide product, hereafter the main features of the “Fire Safe Community” product are outlined along with the Insurance Distribution Directive (IDD) product information template.

7.1.1. What is insured?

The product covers the direct damage to tangible fixed assets, i.e., buildings, lands, and their contents, comprising plant and machinery, industrial and commercial installations, due to wildfires. Fire Safe Community then adds the wildfire coverage with respect to the products that will deliver the new obligation coverages. The focus on tangible fixed assets is the same as the new Italian insurance obligation. A representative product information document is shown in Figure 8.

7.1.2. What is not insured?

The product does not cover any loss from perils other than wildfire. Moreover, it does not cover losses different from direct damages on tangible fixed assets, and, specifically, indoor fires, those related either to personal or company liability, and business interruption.

Even though losses not covered, e.g. those deriving from business interruption, constitute a relevant part of risks related to wildfires, it has been estimated that direct damage are an important part of the value for many business activities, like those operating in agriculture, manufacturing, commerce, tourism and many other sectors, and that the recovery related to properties would reflect into a faster recovery of activities and, then, a reduction of other losses.

FireSafe Community
 Insurance Product Information Document

Disclaimer: this document does not refer to a real insurance product. It is intended just to represent key information of a prototype product.

What is this type of insurance?

FireSafe Community is an insurance product that offers businesses coverage for damage to buildings and their contents related to forest fires.

The product includes discounts linked to the implementation of mitigation measures such as forest management of the territory.

 What is insured?

- ✓ Wildfire and related damages to buildings and their contents, plant and machinery, industrial and commercial installations.

 What is not insured?

- ✗ Perils different than wildfires
- ✗ Losses different than direct damages to buildings and contents.

 Are there any restrictions on cover?

- ! coverage limits have not been considered.

 Where am I covered?

- ✓ Sardinia, Italy

 What are my obligations?

- To provide needed information for the risk assessing at the moment of policy signature.
- During the course of the policy: to declare any new circumstances or change in circumstances likely to lead to a significant and lasting aggravation of the insured risk.
- Other typical insurance obligations.

 When and how do I pay?

- The coverage starts at the date indicated in the policy. It lasts one year and it is tacitly renewable.

 When does the cover start and end?

- The coverage starts at the date indicated in the policy. It lasts one year and it is tacitly renewable.

 How do I cancel the contract?

- The policy can be canceled following usual methods adopted for similar products.

Figure 8: Fire Safe Community product information document

7.1.3. Where is the product valid?

The product is valid in the Sardinia area. Such a geographic perimeter relates to the area where the pricing has been implemented. Here, the financial sustainability of a product limited to this geographical region, has not been investigated. However, it should be noted that the approach could be extended to other areas with similar benefits in terms of pricing.

7.2. Interactions with Demonstrator 8

Based on a set of questions identified to investigate how stakeholders interact with insurance, we analysed the transcriptions of discussions held with local administrators and policy- and decision-makers (LAPM, 19 participants) and shepherds (SH, 17 participants) during two in-person focus groups conducted on 13.11.2023.

The same set of questions have been directly posed to touristic operators (TO, 6 participants) during an online focus group held on 27.09.2024, resulting in more direct responses for this group.

Overall, discussions with LAPM and SH provided valuable insights into the challenges of wildfire risk management and prevention strategies. However, LAPM participants did not explicitly address the adequacy or availability of insurance offerings, while SH participants indicated that insurance is not currently viewed as a central tool for managing wildfire risks. Nevertheless, topics such as planning, prevention, and community resilience suggest opportunities to develop innovative insurance models that integrate natural mitigation measures and community-based strategies to reduce costs.

In contrast, the discussion with TO revealed significant gaps in wildfire risk management and insurance coverage. Tourist operators emphasized the need for clear and comprehensive policies tailored to wildfire risks and expressed interest in exploring innovative solutions, although with many concerns.

How is fire risk managed (is it considered in company security planning and management? Is insurance cover provided)?	
LAPM	<p>Territorial planning is identified by local administrators, policy-makers, and decision-makers as a crucial element for wildfire risk management. However, a lack of specific integrated policies to address wildfire risk is also emphasized. Specifically, all agreed that greater forest and land-use planning is needed to prevent wildfires by integrating agricultural, forestry, and urban policies. Fuel management is identified as the primary lever to reduce risks.</p> <p>The absence of adequate financial resources and local expertise to ensure systematic and coordinated risk management is highlighted as an operational obstacle.</p> <p>There is no direct mention of insurance tools or specific coverage.</p>

<p>SH</p>	<p>The discussion with shepherds and Confagricoltura emphasized the presence of significant obstacles in managing forests and rural areas. Stakeholders highlight bureaucratic constraints, such as restrictions on forestry activities, which hinder efforts to reduce vegetation and improve fire prevention (e.g., legal restrictions on clearing Mediterranean scrub or managing forests; grazing prohibition in areas affected by wildfires for up to 10 years).</p> <p>There is a lack of clear governance and responsibility, as stated by participants who note that both private and public landowners face challenges in maintaining their properties. Public areas often become "no man's land," leading to unmanaged vegetation and heightened fire vulnerability.</p> <p>No reference to insurance in planning and management of the farm.</p>
<p>TO</p>	<p>Even though wildfire risk is perceived as a recurring and intensifying phenomenon, proactive management is still limited. Businesses adhere to mandatory safety measures, such as maintaining vegetation clearance around their premises, but rarely engage in activities beyond their immediate areas. Fire risks from external sources, e.g., surrounding vegetation, are acknowledged but perceived as distant or secondary concerns.</p> <p>TOs implemented basic preventive infrastructure, such as hydrants. Hotels often have direct outdoor access, reducing evacuation risks and calming guest concerns. However, participants note that their actions are limited to legal requirements and immediate surroundings, leaving wildfire risk unaddressed.</p>

<p>Is the current insurance offer for natural hazards (if any) and for fire risk in particular considered adequate for the needs of the company/business?</p>	
<p>LAPM</p>	<p>No explicit references to the adequacy of insurance offerings are present. Stakeholders describe difficulties in coordination between regional agencies and private stakeholders for preventive management. The importance of improving risk awareness is emphasized, which might relate to perceptions of inadequacy in existing solutions.</p>

<p>SH</p>	<p>No explicit references to the adequacy of insurance offerings are present. In general, the participants note that current policies and economic incentives, such as those provided under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), are not aligned with forestry management or wildfire risk reduction. The CAP does not support forest management, leaving landowners with little incentive to maintain wooded areas.</p> <p>In the survey for Shepherds (conducted before the discussion) this question was asked: "Should public authorities oblige people living in high-risk areas to take out fire insurance?"; out of 17 participants, only 2 answered YES, 1 answered "no obligation but incentives", 5 answered "I don't know" and the rest answered NO.</p>
<p>TO</p>	<p>While some participants include fire risk in their policies, they remain unsure if these cover events like wildfires caused by negligence or natural phenomena. One participant worries that insurers might not provide compensation without an identified cause, such as human negligence. Others express dissatisfaction with how claims for catastrophic events, e.g., floods, have been previously handled, revealing a broader distrust in the insurance system's capacity to address natural risks effectively.</p> <p>CMCC & CNR introduce the "catastrophic insurance" policy topic to the discussion, but participants note that wildfire insurance might not cover a risk that in Mediterranean areas is 90% anthropogenic.</p>

<p>What insurance solutions are currently chosen (also considering other natural risks)?</p>	
<p>LAPM</p>	<p>Absence of discussions on existing insurance solutions, although it seems that access to public and private funds is perceived as a challenge, suggesting that insurance instruments might gain traction only if supported.</p>
<p>SH</p>	<p>This point has not been addressed by stakeholders. However, it should be noted here that, since maintenance costs are seen as prohibitive, incentives associated with insurance could maybe play a role in promoting preventive measures.</p>
<p>TO</p>	<p>Participants mention standard fire insurance as part of their policies, but there is limited exploration of specific wildfire coverage. Uncertainty about whether policies cover events like self-ignition or negligence-based fires is a recurring theme. Furthermore, participants highlight obstacles such as ambiguous policy terms and the lack of trust in insurers to compensate for less straightforward claims, as demonstrated in previous experiences with flood-related claims.</p>

Role of the community: Are there existing experiences of this type (insurance coverage proposed or managed through an entity that groups multiple users)?	
LAPM	The need for community involvement to increase resilience and develop shared strategies has been emphasized. Some members of the Forest Service highlighted that local experiences, such as collaboration with the agropastoral sector (e.g., prescribed burning projects with local farmers and shepherds), have successfully reduced wildfires. This demonstrates that community-based approaches can work in specific contexts. The discussion suggests that integrated management strategies could potentially be expanded with the support of innovative financial tools, which might include community insurance models in the future.
SH	The concept of community-based insurance is proposed by CMCC and CNR, presenting some examples from the USA. Some participants express doubt about adopting foreign models, emphasizing the need for solutions tailored to the local context. They stress the importance of political will and regional strategies over external frameworks.
TO	The idea of a collective insurance policy is introduced by CMCC & CNR, where premiums decrease as community members engage in preventive measures like clearing vegetation and creating firebreaks. There are no existing experiences of this type. Participants generally find this concept interesting but foresee challenges: 1) coordinating diverse stakeholders with differing priorities is seen as a significant obstacle; 2) participants express concerns about the cost and feasibility of implementing such a policy on a regional or communal scale; 3) participants express doubts concerning the possibility that a municipality or the Sardinia's regional government act as the primary insurer, sharing costs across municipalities.

How incentivizing would a reduction in insurance costs be based on community aggregation and/or the implementation of natural mitigation measures?	
LAPM	<p>Following elements of discussion related to this topic have been reported:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The need for interventions like a mosaic landscape approach—combining forests, agriculture, and pastures to improve fuel management and reduce wildfire risks—is emphasized. Could these measures theoretically be incentivized through reduced insurance costs? 2. Emphasis is placed on raising awareness among local communities to adopt responsible behaviors. Possibly, such behaviour could align or at least create a fertile environment for insurance solutions. 3. While insurance cost reductions tied to community aggregation are not explicitly discussed, community involvement and land management are identified as crucial tools for reducing risks and overall emergency costs.
SH	<p>Despite the potential benefits briefly presented by CMCC and CNR, participants highlight practical obstacles, such as the high costs of land maintenance discourage individual and collective efforts and the landowner disinterest or absenteeism. These factors can limit the possible application of community-based insurance products.</p>
TO	<p>Overall, it seems that participants agree that linking reduced premiums to preventive actions (e.g., vegetation management, firebreaks) is a promising approach. This model could foster collective action to mitigate risks and provide financial benefits for engaging in fire prevention. Although, concerns remain high about the economic viability of such-policies, especially for low-income individuals in scarce populated areas and the accountability and fairness in distributing the financial burden among participants.</p>

7.3. Data and methods

The nat cat model for the Fire Safe Community product has been developed exploiting wildfire dataset to inform the nat cat model approach described in Section 4. Such datasets and information have been provided by Demonstrator 8 partners, i.e., CMCC, CNR and IIASA and they are here briefly described.

A historical wildfire dataset for the Sardinia area has been arranged collecting data provided by Regional Forestry Corps (Corpo forestale e di vigilanza ambientale, CFVA) and enriched by CMCC and CNR. The dataset comprises wildfires ranging from 2005 to 2022. The dataset reports 23059 fires with an average of about 1350 fires per year. The temporal distribution of events highlights the seasonal dynamics of wildfires (Figure 9).

It has been assumed that the frequency of events reported by this data is congruent with occurrence of events potentially producing damages. Then, it has been used to set the expected number of events per year in Sardinia modeled by the hazard module. Additionally, the distribution of area of events has been adopted to estimate parameters of generated wildfires (Figure 10).

Figure 9: Historical burned area by Sardinia wildfires

Figure 10: Empirical distribution of wildfire area and distribution fitting.

For the Ogliastra area, a specific wildfire modeling has been designed by CMCC and CNR within Demonstrator 8. The output has been elaborated to produce burning probability and loss ratio maps (Figure 11 and 12). The loss rate map was obtained from wildfires' physical features using the approach proposed by El Ezz et al. 2022, which proposes relationships between fire intensity and loss rate. This modeling resulted in an average loss rate map for the analyzed territory.

Figure 11: Burning probability for the Ogliastro area.

Figure 12: Loss Rate for the Ogliastro area.

A similar wildfire modeling activity has been carried out by IIASA by means of the FLAM model. The output consists of burned area and intensity obtained using, as the weather forcing variables, either ERA5 reanalysis data or CMIP6 data (using both historical and projection experiments). Table 2 reports a synthesis of modeling settings. Simulations based on the ERA5 dataset have been used as hazard maps to be used in the nat cat model. In Figure 13, the mean burned area with associated intensity is shown.

Table 2: Datasets used to force wildfire modeling for Sardinia.

Dataset	Coverage perios
ERA5	2005-2021
CMIP6 – Historical	1991-2020
CMIP6 – SSP1-2.6	2021-2070
CMIP6 – SSP3-7.0	2021-2070

Figure 13: Mean burned area for the Sardinia Region.

The hazard module, as described in Section 5.1.1, has been implemented using: the average number of wildfires per year to stochastically simulate the frequency of events; the Sardinia mean burned area map as probability map of event occurrence; and the statistical distribution of events area to assign an area to each event.

Vulnerability has been modeled by estimating the loss rate value to be associated with wildfire events. Within the vulnerability module, the loss rate, that must be associated to exposure elements affected by the events generated in the hazard simulations, is estimated as the specific loss rate value from the Ogliastra loss rate map, if the value falls within the Ogliastra territory. If the exposure element falls outside this area, a constant loss rate value, equal to the average of this map, is adopted.

For the Fire Safe Community product, the reference portfolio (see Figure 14) was derived based on the indications provided by Istat. Specifically, data from the Active Business Statistical Register (ASIA) estimate that in 2022 there are 112,260 active businesses (out of a total of 4,665,423 in Italy). The size of the reference portfolio is evaluated by assuming an incidence, for the Fire Safe Community product, equal to 5% of the total number of businesses in Sardinia, i.e., 5,613 businesses.

The distribution of policies within the territory was carried out adapting to the density of buildings following the same approach, based on GHSL, described for the Landslide product. The range of exposure values has been set equal to 10000-300000 € similarly to the Landslide product.

Figure 14: Reference portfolio used for the Fire Safe Community product development.

7.4. Pricing

As indicated in Section 5, a pure premium rate map is obtained intersecting the SES events with a gridded portfolio with unit exposure. Here, a spatial resolution of 250 m has been used to produce this map. Then, the AEP curve is derived with reference to the reference portfolio. This curve provides the total portfolio loss to be expected with probability levels described in terms of return period. Along with the AEP curve, another relationship, the OEP (Occurrence Expected Probability) is computed considering the year-max loss to be expected with a given return period. In Figure 15 the AEP and OEP curves, derived for the Fire Safe Community product, are shown.

Figure 15: AEP and OEP curves.

The *AAL* and the AEP^{200} loss are combined, as indicated in Section 5, to estimate the *m* multiplier that transforms the pure premium rate map into the finite premium rate map (Figure 16).

The premium rate map allows for the estimation of policy premiums based on the amount of exposure for which they are underwritten. By associating such values with the reference portfolio previously described, it is possible to characterize the premium associated with each policy. The distribution of these policy premiums is shown in Figure 17. The average value of the reference portfolio premiums is 29 €.

Figure 16: Premium Rate obtained from the nat cat model.

Figure 17: Distribution of premiums of the Fire Safe Community reference portfolio.

As outlined in the concept, the Fire Safe Community product includes a discount based on the adoption by groups of users who can be associated with risk mitigation actions through forestry management operations. In order to model the impact of such actions on insurance premiums, a specific vulnerability model has been developed. This model is based on the work of Martinez et al. (2021) that examines the potential of ecological forestry to reduce wildfire risk and, consequently, insurance premiums. The study focuses on the Placer County, California, area and the resources of the French Meadows Project, a landscape-scale ecological forestry project, as the basis for analyzing risk reduction benefits of the ecological forestry activities. This study quantifies the effects of ecological forestry management on a Large Wildfire Potential (LWP) used to score the potential of large fires based on vegetation types. In particular, LWP takes into account the resistance to control of four classes of flame lengths. The effects of ecological forestry management are modeled partially downgrading some classes to more “controllable” classes.

In the Fire Safe Community model a vulnerability curve has been calibrated taking into account the magnitude parameter of a specific version of LWP. In particular, the same classes of potential flame lengths have been derived based on Corine Land Cover classes. The same classes downgrading was used to estimate effects of ecological forestry management activities.

This approach allowed us to estimate the reduction on pure and finite premium. In particular, for the reference portfolio, an average reduction of the pure premium equal to 10% is found. This value was assumed as the discount to apply for ecological forestry management activities. The discount is then applied to customers whose assets fall into areas where wildfire reduction forestry management activities are carried out by the customer itself or a group of subjects. All the companies involved in forestry management activities are eligible for this kind of discount.

8. Conclusions

This document describes the development of innovative insurance product prototypes, as part of the activities conducted within Task 3.3 “Insurance and risk financing instruments for DRR and local resilience”. The requirements for the development of these products were based on interactions with stakeholders of the involved demonstrators, the insurance gap related to natural risks, with particular reference to companies, also considering the regulations determined by the new catastrophic coverage obligation introduced in Italy. In the context of innovative insurance solutions for Disaster Risk Reduction, we have developed and presented two prototypes of insurance products, designed for testing in regional and sub-regional contexts. Both prototypes are grounded in catastrophe models, yet they offer distinct approaches to managing natural hazards. Landslide First Rescue is conceptualized as an emergency tool that provides rapid compensation following a landslide event. The claim-settlement process is streamlined compared to traditional insurance products, as it eliminates the need for adjusters and relies solely on predefined thresholds corroborated by media reports or similar evidence. While this product alone could not be sufficient for a full recovery in case of largely impacted events, it provides a helpful and quick recovery tool that could be supported by other classic insurance products. On the other hand, Fire Safe Community has a more classic approach in terms of claims-settlement structure, but it includes an innovative reward mechanism in case of risk reduction actions developed by the policy holders.

From a broader perspective, the importance of the role of the insurance industry in reducing catastrophic risks has been widely recognized, both as a financial tool for individual and collective protection, and as a facilitator and promoter of other governance actions, both public and private, with particular reference to the promotion of resilience and risk mitigation. To achieve this framework, insurance companies must select and implement suitable innovative ideas.

The products selected within this project activity should be considered an initial exploration of, respectively, parametric policies (DEM 3) and insurance that rewards mitigation actions based on forest management activities carried out by communities operating in a specific territory (DEM 8). For both products, a pricing model that provides a cost of policies proportional to the risk assumed has been developed. This approach corresponds to a fair distribution of risk mutuality and is consistent with the indications of the new catastrophic obligation recently introduced in Italy, which suggests this principle of proportionality. For both presented prototypes, the essential elements of the product and some pricing examples demonstrating the economic sustainability of the policies (excluding other necessary expenses for product commercialization) have been defined. In this study, the two products were evaluated considering single perils. The possible coupling with guarantees related to other perils or other types of coverage was not considered. Further evaluations related to the financial aspects of these products and their framing within a multi-hazard product will be assessed in future activities that will be carried out in Deliverable 3.7.

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